

SCHOOLS ETHICAL ASPECTS FROM TEACHERS PERSPECTIVES			Education
			Keywords: Ethics, teacher, ethical concerns, school.
Mergime Tefiki	University of Tetovo, Tetovo, North Macedonia		
Atixhe Maksuti	South East European University, Tetovo, North Macedonia		
Abstract			
<p>The main purpose of the study is to verify different approach of ethics in teachers behaviour, are teachers informed for ethical norms, does schools have a written ethical code, whether schools organise trainings related to school ethics codes, to verify if schools have reporting procedures of unethical behaviors and how unethical behaviors are punished, to ascertain whether people with high integrity are rewarded at school. Main problem of the study is to define ethical aspects of schools in teachers behaviour. The sample of the study from a total of 60 teachers, both male and female from elementary and high school teachers from several schools in Tetovo, Kicevo and Gostivar. The measuring instrument used was the created by professors from Baylor University. The items were adapted by the authors, with previous online research. The questionnaire with a total of 30 items have measured ethical aspects. The research confirmed that half of the respondents told that their school has a written ethical code, and 74% of them think that justice and equality are valued higher for a society, the results show also that respondents value loyalty at higher extend.</p>			

Introduction

The main motivation of conducting this type of research came as a necessity and as a consequence of the lack of literature in the Albanian language on ethics in schools from the perspective of teachers and different aspects of ethical issues on school related topics. Ethics in schools is a very important factor that reflects on the behavior and the general atmosphere of the school. The code of ethics is designed to help the teacher to make the right decisions in cases of ethical dilemmas he faces while practicing his profession.

School ethics from the perspective of teachers assessing all school spaces such as sports fields, school yards and all other facilities that are part of the school, how teachers see it and what ethical climate prevails in schools. From the result we see that most of the teachers from schools that were part of the study said that schools have a written code of ethics, schools sometimes report unethical behaviors in the school whether they are from students, teachers or other school staff. The data show that ethical behaviors in school are not valued and sufficiently rewarded.

Educators worldwide face unprecedented obstacles in balancing local, national, and global conventions, as well as moral and ethical ideals, in the process of educating children. While instilling a sense of citizenship is a vital purpose of public education, doing so at the expense of socializing children for their futures in a global society is becoming increasingly unsustainable (Sutton, 2005).

Professional behavior is governed by ethics, which ensures the profession's continuity and survival (Deshach, 2014). Studying and teaching ethics is critical to the promotion of ethical practices reflected positively on the methodology of teaching, as well as on the relations between all elements of the school community.

They are based largely on the availability of a positive trend towards the profession and represent a framework and increasing the role of the teacher in the educational process (Forster, 2012).

According to Afifi (2005), imposing a code of ethics or norms of conduct on a teacher in moral terms provides a lot of room for discretion, so the instructor decides what is moral or immoral within these rules. Improper application of these general norms robs them of their content and turns them into formal actions with no purpose. Capli (2015) stated that, "the teaching profession's Code of Ethics is necessary for maintaining control over the educational process and preventing it from deviating".

According to Mansour and Talafh (2009), ethical thinking is the ultimate purpose of education, which Simon refers to as "education as an ethical vision." Ethics, according to Al-Zubi (2013), is a charter that lays out the concepts, beliefs, and responsibilities that teachers must follow in order to accomplish their jobs to the best of their abilities.

Because education is a moral activity, it cannot function without values, which determine educational action and direction. Mutraja (2004) has demonstrated the importance of values in the educational process; values serve as the foundation for achieving educational goals. Professional ethics is important because it guides individual actions and establishes a work base that is accepted by practitioners in the workplace. As a result, anyone who breaches them risks being humiliated, fired, or penalized (Ajaji, 2012). Burgess (1989) identified four ethical dilemmas that are relevant to educational research: research sponsorship, research relations, informed consent and data dissemination. These continue to remain key ethical dilemmas and concerns that should receive consideration by researchers. There are interesting related studies on how moral attitudes or behaviour at times change, e.g., Cappelen et al. (2011), Ellingsen and Johannesson (2005), Almås et al. (2010) and Fan (2000).

Methodology

Based on the literature on the importance of ethics in school we come to the formulation of the research problem. Do schools have a written code of ethics that regulates ethical issues? The research was conducted with the descriptive method. The descriptive method aims to describe the actual situation in a group of people or population. In other words, descriptive methods are not intended to measure the effect of one variable on other variables, but primarily to describe them.

A typical example of research to which the descriptive method is applied is when describing the trend of crime movement among adolescents or when describing the distribution of smoking or attitudes towards various issues in certain age groups, etc. (Osmani, Q. 2020).

P.1 Are trainings held in your schools regarding the school code of ethics?

Q.2 Do schools have procedures for reporting unethical behavior?

Q.3 Are people rewarded with integrity in your school?

Q.4 Are penalties for unethical behavior strictly applied in your school?

The Purpose of the Research

The purpose of the research is deskriptive. Also its Purpose is to describes the presence of the study variable and to collect data, as well as to pave the way for other studies. To look at the school's approach to various aspects of ethics; To validate the attitudes of teachers towards ethical aspects; Find out how schools approach and undertake unethical events.

Research tasks

To shed light on the concepts and approach to ethics in schools. Identify the approach of schools during unethical behaviors. Collect data where theoretical and practical aspects can be compared.

Research Hypotheses

Schools have a written code of ethics. We assume that values of justice and equality for teachers are more important. Assume that schools condemn unethical behavior. Assume that ethical behaviors are not sufficiently rewarded

Test Reliability

From the results of the table above from the questionnaire school ethics from the perspective of teachers we have derived the reliability of the questionnaire. The total number of items in the questionnaire is divided into two parts where the first part includes items related to school ethics from the perspective of teachers and the second part includes questions related to personal evaluation as a teacher on ethical issues.

From the test results we see that we have a high reliability of the questionnaire used in the study $\alpha = 0.87$. The total number of the questionnaire is 19. Data collection was performed through the online platform Google Forms.

Discussion

The purpose of the study is to collect data and to describe the results of actual situation of ethical aspects on school and teacers behaviour towards those issues. The results are shown below with graphics appearance to be more clear.

Figure 1. Results of the question Does your school has a written ethical code

Our hypothesis was that schools have a written ethical code.

Hypothesis 1. Schools have a written ethical code.

From the total number of respondents, 46.7% of them said that there is always a written code of ethics in their schools.

The highest percentage of results show that schools have a written code of ethics and teachers are aware of this.

Table 1. Descriptive data on the values of fairness and equality of teachers

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Always	42	70.0	70.0	70.0
Often	15	25.0	25.0	95.0
Rarely	3	5.0	5.0	100.0
Total	60	100.0	100.0	

Hypothesis 2. We assume that values of fairness and equality for teachers are more important. From the results we have obtained we notice that the highest percentage is that teachers pay special attention to values such as justice and 70% equality. From this we understand that our hypothesis is proved.

Table 2. Descriptive data for reporting unethical behavior in schools

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Always	12	20.0	20.0	20.0
Often	21	35.0	35.0	55.0
Rarely	21	35.0	35.0	90.0
Never	6	10.0	10.0	100.0
	60	100.0	100.0	

To the question whether your school has procedures for reporting unethical behaviors we received an answer with the same percentage that often and rarely report unethical behaviors by 35%.

Table 3. Descriptive data for reporting unethical behavior in schools

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Always	17	28.3	28.3	28.3
Often	21	35.0	35.0	63.3
Rarely	17	28.3	28.3	91.7
Never	5	8.3	8.3	100.0
Total	60	100.0	100.0	

Hypothesis 3. We suppose that schools condemn unethical behavior. From the hypothesis we have assumed we see that the results have the same percentage in both options presented always emphasize that they condemn unethical behavior and also some of the subjects claim that they rarely condemn unethical behavior in schools.

Table 4. Descriptive data show whether ethical behaviors are rewarded in schools

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Always	8	13.3	13.3	13.3
Often	13	21.7	21.7	35.0
Rarely	17	28.3	28.3	63.3
Never	22	36.7	36.7	100.0
Total	60	100.0	100.0	

The data show that ethical behaviors with a higher percentage is that they are never rewarded which we see from the results in the table above with the frequency $F = 22$.

Conclusion

Discussions and recommendations of the research conducted in relation to the defined variable, after interpreting the data from the results we have come to some conclusions and also suggesting more detailed research.

Some of the Recommendations

It can be argued that education is also an ethical endeavor. You can learn norms easily, but you can not easily learn to obey these rules if you do not learn ethics. Therefore, teaching ethics occupies an important and necessary place in education. More than providing knowledge, teaching is considered a moral activity (Seghedin, 2014) and teachers are expected to play the role of moral agents engaged in improving society.

Other recommendation

- Trainings for teachers in order to get acquainted with ethical issues and how to deal with unethical behaviors of students and school staff;
- Inform school staff and students that they are free to report any unethical behavior they see inside the school, yard, gym or any facility that is part of the school;
- We recommend finding appropriate mechanisms where appropriate ethical behavior will be rewarded;
- Improving the ethics of school staff through continuous professional development during work;
- Increase cooperation between teachers, students and parents to improve ethics in the education system;
- Schools must have written and defined ethical behaviors which must also be implemented by school staff.

References

- Afifi, S. M. (2005). Professional ethics of the teacher: Arab Organization for Administrative Development, Arab League.
- Ajaji, A. A. (2012). The reality of implementing the teaching code of Ethics from the perspective of educational supervisors and principals of secondary schools in Riyadh.
- Almås, Ingvild, Alexander Cappelen, Erik. Sorensen, and Bertil Tungodden (2010). "Fairness and the Development of Inequality Acceptance."
- Al-Zubi, R. (2013). The degree of cooperating teachers' commitment to the ethics of the Teaching profession from the perspective of female trainees at Al-Bayt University.
- Burgess, R.G. (1989) The ethics of Educational Research London: Falmer Press.
- Capli, F. A. (2015). The role of school principals in promoting teaching ethics among teachers from principals and teachers perspective in Makkah public schools.
- Cappelen, Alexander, Astri Drange Hole, Erik Sørensen, and Bertil Tungodden. (2011). "The Importance of Moral Reflection and Self-reported Data in a Dictator Game with Production."
- Deshach, N. (2014). The Profession of Education, Ethics and the Role of Teacher.
- Ellingsen, Tore, and Magnus Johannesson. (2005). "Does Impartial Deliberation Breed Fair Behavior?"
- Fan, Chinn-Ping. (2000). "Teaching Children Cooperation- an Application of Experimental Game Theory," Journal of Economic Behavior and Organization.
- Forster, D. J. (2012). Codes of Ethics in Australian Education: Towards a National Perspective. Australian Journal of Teacher Education, 37(9).
<https://doi.org/10.14221/ajte.2012v37n9.4>
- Osmani, O. (2021) Metodologjia në Psikologji. Arbëria Design.

- Mansour, H. K., & Talafh, H. A. (2009). The System of Ethical Values Included in the Books of Islamic Education for the Basic Stage in Jordan.
- Murtaja, A. M. M. (2004). The extent of practicing ethics among secondary school students from their teachers' perspective in Gaza.
- Seghedin, E. (2014). From the teachers professional ethics to the personal professional responsibility. *Acta Didactica Napocensia*.
- Sutton, M. (2005). The Globalization of Multicultural Education. *Indiana Journal of Global Legal Studies*, 12(1), 96-108.